

Monoclinic Double Tungstate Thin-Disk lasers at 2 microns

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OUTLINE

*Motivation and introduction. The **monoclinic double tungstates***

*Fabrication of the **thin-disk** structures*

*Spectroscopy of the **Ho** ions*

*Laser setup for the **Ho thin-disk** laser*

Achieved results

Conclusion and future work

MOTIVATION

State of the art. Tm –based thin-disk lasers

500 μm thick, 10 at.% Tm:YAG: up to 2 W ($T = -30^\circ \text{C}$), *A. Dienes et al., CLEO'98.*

650 μm thick, 6 at.% Tm:YAG: up to 4 W ($T = -17^\circ \text{C}$), *N. Berner et al., ASSL'99.*

- 4 bounces of the pump(8 pump passes)

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200-500 μm thick, 5 at.% Tm:Lu₂O₃: 0.5 W, *M. Schellhorn et al., ASSP, ATuB14 (2011).*

- 12 bounces of the pump

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250 μm thick, 12 at.% Tm:LLF: 21 W @1910 nm *G. Stoeppler et al., Opt. Lett. 37, 1163 (2012).*

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Vey complex pump scheme

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State of the art. Ho –based thin-disk lasers

400 μm , 2 at.% Ho:YAG: 9.4 W @2090 nm, slope efficiency η of ~50% *M. Schellhorn, Appl. Phys. B85, 549 (2006)*

- 12 bounces of the pump (typical for YAG thin-disks), Ho-concentration limited because of upconversion losses
- pumped by a Tm:YLF laser

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400 μm , 2 at.% Ho:YAG: 15 W @2090 nm *J. Speiser et al., SPIE 7912, 79120C (2011)* and *Proc. of SPIE 8547, 85470E-1-11 (2012)*.

- 12 bounces of the pump, Ho-concentration limited because of upconversion losses.
- pumped by a Tm: fiber laser

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Even higher output power, 22 W with η ~27% was achieved in a similar mutipass-pumped Ho:YAG laser using an InP diode. *G. Renz, Proc. of SPIE 9342, 93421W (2015)*.

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GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Our aim was to develop a **Ho thin-disk** laser with
simplified pump geometry based on the **monoclinic**
double tungstate crystals

INTRODUCTION

Monoclinic double tungstates

Substituted ions:

Y^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Lu^{3+}

Trivalent active ions:

Yb^{3+} , Tm^{3+} , Er^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Ho^{3+}

Structural and thermal properties

High doping levels for the active ions

Moderate thermal conductivity

"Athermal" thermo-optic behaviour

example: *KLuW* crystal

Ln^{3+} spectroscopic properties

Large transition cross-sections

Broad absorption and emission bands

Weak concentration-quenching

Strong Raman activity

V. Petrov, et al., Laser Photonics Rev. 1, 179 (2007).

INTRODUCTION

- ⇒ Ideal suited for the thin disk laser concept
- ⇒ Disk thickness $< 100 \mu\text{m}$ sufficient absorption.
- ⇒ Epitaxial structures required
- ⇒ Single bounce pumping possible: Typically ~ 12 bounces of the pump (24 pump passes).
- ⇒ Reduced complexity of the pump geometry

Thin-Disk laser based on $50 \mu\text{m}$ Yb(32%):KLuW epitaxy

S. Rivier et al., Opt. Lett. 33, 735 (2008).

FABRICATION of the THIN DISK STRUCTURES

MDT substrates.

Top-Seeded Solution Growth (TSSG) method.
Oriented normal to the *b*-axis.
They are 1 – 1.5 mm-thick.

Epitaxies.

Liquid Phase Epitaxy (LPE) method

FABRICATION of the THIN DISK STRUCTURES

SPECTROSCOPY of Ho^{3+} in MDT CRYSTALS

Larger gain for $E // N_m$

Absorption and emission cross-section of **Ho:KYW**. $5I_7 \leftrightarrow 5I_8$ transition near 2000 nm. Light polarization $E // N_m$

LASER SETUP for the *Ho:KYW THIN-DISK*

The **pump source** was a Tm fiber laser (model IFL15, LISA laser products, OHG) emitting up to 12.5 W at 1960 nm (FWHM = 1.5 nm, unpolarized output with $M^2 \sim 1$).

LASER RESULTS

For $T_{OC} = 3\%$, the max. $P_{out} = 1.01$ W at 2057 nm with $\eta = 60\%$ (with respect to the absorbed pump power, P_{abs}).

No thermal roll-over was observed when using this OCs.

Using the chopper (in quasi-CW mode, duty cycle (1:2) with the optimum $T_{OC} = 3\%$, the peak output power reached 1.10 W with an increased $\eta = 66\%$ (due to the relaxed heat problems).

LASER RESULTS

Typical laser emission spectra (2057 nm) for the **Ho:KYW thin-disk** laser for various OCs (CW mode, single bounce, $P_{\text{abs}} = 1.52 \text{ W}$). Agreement with the gain spectra.

LASER RESULTS

Comparison of the output performance of the **Ho:KYW** thin-disk laser in CW and quasi-CW operation modes for 1 and 2 bounces of the pump, $T_{OC} = 3\%$.

Worse mode matching produced lower η and higher threshold.

Pump absorption: 1 bounce **14%**, 2 bounces **25%**

LASER RESULTS

Spatial profiles measured at different P_{abs} (CW mode, $T_{\text{OC}} = 1.5\%$).

Astigmatism of the thermal lens

$$M_x^2 = 3.1$$

$$M_y^2 = 1.6$$

Spatial profiles of the output laser beam measured at (a) low $P_{\text{abs}} = 0.39$ W and (b) high $P_{\text{abs}} = 1.78$ W (CW, single bounce of the pump, $T_{\text{OC}} = 3\%$).

A and B – major and minor semiaxes of the elliptic laser beam;

X'_1 and X'_3 – principal axes of the thermal expansion tensor of KYW.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

1- A CW **Ho:KYW/KYW** thin-disk laser generated 1.01 W (~2 W) at 2056-2059 nm with a slope efficiency η of 60% (55%) for a single (double) bounce of the pump at 1960 nm.

2- The spectroscopy of the **Ho** ions indicates good suitability of the **Ho:KYW/KYW** epitaxy for thin-disk lasers; while thermo-optic effects can be an issue.

In future:

1- We plan to optimize the **Ho** concentration (1-7 at.%), the pump spot size and the pump source.

2- Pulsed operation.

Optics Letters

Holmium thin-disk laser based on Ho:KY(WO₄)₂/KY(WO₄)₂ epitaxy with 60% slope efficiency and simplified pump geometry

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